

Research

Stability Analysis of Hussainabad Landslide, Gilgit-Baltistan, Pakistan

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Abstract: This study presents a detailed geological and geotechnical analysis of Hussainabad landslide, Pakistan. The study site is located in the Hunza valley along Indus River at Miacher and Hussainabad Village in Gilgit Baltistan. Due to proximity of the major tectonic feature, the rock are highly foliated, folded and fractured highly foliated rocks of slates and schists are the dominant character of the site geology. The induced dynamic stresses have altered the stability level of valley slopes. The study has the main focus on contributing factors responsible for its instability together with stability analysis using computer program slide software of Rocscience 5.0. The input parameter of rock mass was evaluated by field investigations and laboratory testing, for the rock mass characterization Discontinuity survey was conducted. The results shows that Tension cracks found on the upper slope are not persistent to the side slopes or the toe on both sides. They can generate large scale movement by their intersection with joint set J-1 dipping southward, provided shearing though intact parts between joints takes place. This phenomenon is likely to occur on earthquake of 6.5 magnitudes or 33% saturation. In dry conditions, without seismic loading, slope is fairly stable with factor of safety of 1.34, however, saturation or strong motion can trigger the movement. Engineering characters of rocks has been greatly affected by intense stresses due to presence of major structural features such as Main karakoram thrust (MKT) and it's off shoots. This study recommends protection parameters for Hussain Abad landslide stability.

Keywords: Landslide, Stability, Tectonic, Slope, Earthquake, Seismic,

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Introduction

The study sites are located in the Hunza valley along Indus River at Miachar and Hussainabad villages in Gilgit Baltistan Pakistan. The region is well known for world tallest snow peaks and three mountainous ranges, Himalaya, Karakorum and Hindukush. The area remains sever cold and intensive snow fall during winter and have pleasant

summer. This region is highly vulnerable for several landslides, over the past several decades many catastrophic event has been happened resulting may human and economic loss. The study area is exactly lies at the fringe of regional fault called MKT (Main Karakorum Thrust Fault) which is boundary between Indian and Eurasian plate. Due to this proximity of the source tectonic feature of northern suture near Chalt, the area has been intensely folded and faulted. The past tectonic history is responsible for extensive fracturing of the rocks. Highly foliated rocks of slates, phyllites and schists are the dominant character of the site geology. The induced dynamic stresses have altered the stability level of valley slopes. Huge movements of earth materials in the study area can destroy structures, human settlements; agricultural lands, cut off transport system, block the roads modify landscape and block the river. River blockage may be the most hazardous phenomenon causing submergence of upstream towns and strategic highway like Attabad landslide that has happened in 2009, this landslide blocked the main route Karakorum high way which is least route between china and Pakistan. The study has the main focus on contributing factors responsible for its instability together with stability analysis using computer program slide software of Rocscience 5.0. The input parameter of rock mass was evaluated by field investigations and laboratory testing.

Literature Review

Landslide are one of the most dangerous geological phenomena that pose important danger to modern developed societies, since they are closely connected to human and property losses and have important economic impact on the regional economy [1]. In recent years the assessment of landslide hazard and risk has become a topic of major interest for both geoscientists and engineering professionals as well as for the community and the local administrations in many parts of the world.[2], Landslides are very common natural hazard phenomenon in mountainous areas of the world especially high mountains like Himalaya [3-5]. In 1981 Varnes estimated that from 1971 to 1974 nearly 600 people were killed every year world-wide as a consequence of slope failures. Geologically, the Himalayan Mountain range is the youngest and most dynamic system in the world [6]. The Pakistani Himalaya is specifically famous for the recurrent seismic activities, landsliding and flash floods [7, 8].The most northern park of Pakistan which occupied by world famous three mountainous ranges, Karakoram, Hindukush and Himalaya. Over the past couple of centuries many natural disasters hits urban areas resulting loss of hundreds of human and economic loss. In 2009 a catastrophic landslide occurred in Karakorum range Attabad, Hunza, 4 km nearby the study area which has killed 14 people and created a huge water reservoir which engulfed three villages at upstream areas that caused loss more than billions of dollars. Similarly many slope failure events happened in this valley in the past caused many human loss. Six major landslides were identified in this valley within 20 square kilometers in the Hunza valley, FOCUS(Focus Humanitarian assistance Pakistan).researchers have also estimated that one-third of the total world landslides occur in the Himalayan region [9]. In this region, the problem of landsliding varies from small scale slope failure to heavy landsliding. The impact of slope movements in the study sites depends upon their type, depth of movement rate of movement, stresses from environment, volume of materials involved and the nearness of these slides to important structures. It depends on several interrelated factors including lithology, slope gradient, climate, land cover and drainage that bring landslide susceptibility[10-14]. Factors like slope geometry, strength of the material, discontinuity behavior, weak zones, geological disturbance and rainfall can initiate the slope failure[15-20].

Various researchers have conducted extensive research dealing with types of the landslide, its classification, causes, and analysis and stabilization methods. Waseem et al. [21] studied the slope failure at Qalandar Abad, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Pakistan. The determination of the factor of safety (FOS) for slope stability was carried out with the Limit Equilibrium Method (LEM) on GeoStudio Software. In Pakistan, Himalayas are the most affected areas by a landslide [22, 23]. The stability of the landslide can be enhanced with the increment in the slope angle [24, 25].The human activities which are intended and oriented towards development of the area for settlements proclamation of cultivable land, construction of roads or widening of existing roads or excavation for other civil engineering purposes, lead to cause instability problems. Huge movements of earth materials in the project area can destroy structures,

human settlements; agricultural lands, cut off transport system, block the roads modify landscape and block the river. River blockage may be the most hazardous phenomenon causing submergence of upstream towns and strategic highway like Attabad landslide. Small-scale movements on the other hand are affecting local structures, individual houses, communication system and terrace agriculture [26].

The geotectonic development of the Northern Areas of Pakistan during late Cretaceous to Cenozoic involved three tectonic elements, i.e. the Indo-Pakistan shield and its northern sedimentary cover (Indian Mass), the rocks deposited on the southern part of the Eurasian Mass, and the Kohistan Island Arc Sequence [27]. From Archaean times, the Indian Sub-Continent was a part of Gondwanaland, which consisted of the continents of South America, Africa, [28] Antarctica, Australia and India. A vast stretch of the Tethys Sea existed between the Indo-Australian part of Gondwanaland and the Eurasian Mass. About 130 million years ago, the Indian Ocean plate broke away from Gondwanaland and started drifting towards Eurasia with the simultaneous consumption of the Tethys Sea plate in between [29]. As a result of subduction, the Kohistan Island Arc Sequence was produced to the north of the subduction zone. The first contact of this Island Arc was with the Indo-Pakistan plate, which finally collided with the Eurasian Mass. The Kohistan Island Arc Sequence is juxtaposed between the Indo-Pakistan plate and the Eurasian plate. A major thrust fault called the Main Mantle Thrust (MMT) separates the Indian Mass from the Kohistan Island Arc Sequence while another thrust fault called the Main Karakoram Thrust (MKT) marks the boundary between the Kohistan Island Arc Sequence and the Eurasian Mass.

Methodology

The site investigations executed during field studies are detailed below

Topographic mapping

Topographic survey of the problematic area was carried out and a map was produced on a scale of 1:1000 with 3-meter contour interval. It was used as a base map for geological mapping, and landslide feature marking. A survey team comprising experienced surveyors, under the supervision of a geotechnical expert, carried out the topographic survey using Total Station survey equipment. The team picked up important features of the project site. The baseline initial control points were established on each site assigning them the coordinates with the help of GPS. Other control points were established with respect to those initial points and their positions are given on the topographic maps in Fig. 1.

Geological mapping

Regional as well as site-specific geologic studies were carried out to determine the role of geologic factors in mass movement. Detailed geologic map showing the site-specific engineering geologic features was prepared using topographic map as base information. These features included contacts between various geologic materials and structural discontinuities. Total station instrument and Brunton compass were used for measurement purpose during geological mapping. The geologic maps are given in Fig. 2 respectively. The cross-sections along different lines have been drawn to depict the sub surface geologic conditions are given in Fig 3.

Fig. 1: Topographic and landslide map

Fig. 2: Geological map of the study area

Fig. 3: Cross-Section A,A of Hussainabad

Field Observations & Measurements

The geo-environmental conditions were observed during field studies related to the slope stability of the study sites. Orientation of slope and its location with respect to surrounding geo-environmental framework was assessed in the field. The distribution of loose unconsolidated materials and their geo-engineering character related to engineering properties was observed such as grain size and its percentage, thickness, shape of cobbles boulders, their inter-locking, compactness, percentage of finer material, their densification etc.

The relationship of different discontinuities with slope geometry was observed and established in the field which is controlling the stability of rock slopes.

Surface water conditions including sources, flow pattern, runoff and infiltration etc. was observed and recorded.

Results and Discussion

The slopes along Hunza River and Karakorum Highway in the area of study sites are generally steep with some vertical slopes and overhangs. Slope forming rocks are moderately to highly foliated and fractured. However, massive rocks are also found at places wherein slopes have been cut very steep/overhangs.

Some slopes are formed in the overburden of alluvial, fluvial and glacial nature. These slopes generally keep on moving as debris falls, flows and rotational slides particularly in the season of high recharge.

The slope may be divided into three segments in view of slope orientation such as eastern slope behind Hussainabad village, Southern slope towards bridge and the Western slope behind Khizarabad(Fig 1).

Eastern Slope The village Hussainabad is located between toe of Eastern slope and the river on a fertile cultivated terrace. The average slope behind the village is 45°. Rocks of the outcrop slope are slates, schists and phyllites with lenses of massive basic to ultramafic rocks at places. Slates and phyllites are moderately foliated and fractured. Foliation is dipping into slope with an average angle of 45° (Fig. 3). Two prominent joint sets are found on this slope i.e. J-1 and J-2 (Table 1).

Joint set J-1 is striking at right angle to foliation and dipping at about 80° west (Table 1). Joint set J-2 is nearly parallel to slope (N70°E) and dipping towards slope i.e. SE at an average angle of 48° (Fig. 3). Slope orientation is generally

N50°E and inclined at an average angle of 45SE. Joint set J-2 is nearly parallel to slope and dipping towards slope at about the angle of slope inclination.

Fig. 4: Cross-Section B, B Hussainabad

Table. 1: Field measurements and Evaluations of Discontinuity Parameters eastern slope

Joint Set No	Strike	Dip	Spacing (Cm)	Persistence	Aperture (mm)	Nature of infilling	Surface roughness	JRC	Schmidt Hardness	Column above Joint Set (h)	JCS (MPa)	Normal Load KN*/m2	Ø Peak
J-1	N15° E	80°NW	40	7.5	14	clay	rough	8	15	4	19	100	43.2
J-1	N20° E	75°NW	55	9	12	clay	rough	4	14	7.5	17	187.5	32.8
j-2	N70° E	50°SE	90	4	15	clay	rough	5	17	3.5	25	87.5	37
j-2	N72° E	48°SE	70	3.25	12	clay	rough	4	15	4	22	100	34

The slope movements likely to occur on this face are plane failure along J-2 and rock fall as a result of intersection of foliations, joint sets and random joints (fig: 6). Large scale block slide in this direction is unlikely in view of rock structure in relation to slope geometry. Block size varies from small to as large as 1x1.5m with elongated shape. Extensive rock fall has occurred in the past and damaged cultivated lands and houses. Block size moved down is as mentioned above. No cracks in the houses or in the cultivated terrace are observed or reported by the locals.

Southern Slope (Towards Bridge) This slope is dipping towards River Bridge at an angle of 45°-50° south. Slope orientation at this spot is almost East- West taking a sharp turn towards North West (Fig. 1).

Fig. 5: Cross-Section C,C of Hussainabad

No settlements are located between the toe of this slope and the river. River in this area is close to the toe of the slope. Foliation is striking N70°W and dipping opposite to the slope at an angle of about 75° (Table 2). Joint set J-1 is almost parallel to slope and dipping towards slope at an angle of 40° to 48° South (Table 2). Joint set J-2 is striking N55E and dipping towards North West. The rock in this part of the slope is moderately foliated and highly fractured. Intersection of foliation and joint has turned the rock into blocks of small to very large size (2x2m) depending upon the fracture frequency (Plate-10). Block size is even larger (3 x3m) at the sharp bend of the outcrop slope little west of bridge site (Fig: 9). Rock falls are very frequent along with some plane failures on joint set J-1(Fig: 7). Large scale movement may also occur along joint set J-1 and the tension cracks Fig.1 & 4.

Western Slope

Western slope is located in the outcrop of similar rock conditions. Settlements of Khizarabad are located between the toe of the slope and the river on a fertile cultivated terrace. The terrace comprises thick over burden composed of dominantly clayey silt along with some sand and gravels (Fig. 2). Rock outcrop is moderately foliated weathered and fractured. Foliation and joints are intersecting each other to form blocks of various sizes generally from small to very large. Large occasional blocks of even larger size are also found. Rock condition and structural pattern leads to cause rock falls. In recent past extensive rock fall has occurred causing damage to houses and cultivated lands.

Rock falls and small scale plane failures are most likely modes of slope movement on all the three slopes. Large scale movement is likely to occur towards southern slope (Bridge side) as a result of intersection of tension cracks and joint set J-1 (Fig. 4).

Fig 6: Source of rock fall on eastern slope

Fig 7: Rock falls, debris fall and plane

Fig 8: Large blocks of massive rocks

Fig 9: Rock broken to larger blocks west of bridge

Rock falls and small scale plane failures are common modes of slope movement due to favorable slope geometry in relation to rock structure as described in preceding description. The large scale movement is likely to occur on the southern slope Fig. 4 due to presence of tension cracks and joint set J-1 (table 2).

Plane failure analysis is believed to be valid for the prevailing geotechnical conditions of the slope.

Rocplane software of Rocscience was used for the analysis purpose.

Slope Geometry

Slope orientation E-W

Slope angle = 47°S

Slope height = 400m

Rock Parameters

Following strength parameters have been adopted in view of field measurements and literature review;

Friction angle, $\phi = 30^\circ$

Cohesion, $C = 0.24 \text{ MPa}$

Density = 2600 kg/m^3

Assumptions:

- Joint set J-1 (Fig. 4) is assumed to be the potential failure plane by the intersection of tension cracks.
- The persistence of J-1 is 2to5m in general (table 2). It is assumed that intact rock in between the joints may be sheared through and cohesion has been taken on little higher side.

Factor of safety (FOS) at static loading in dry conditions (Fig. 11) = 1.34

- FOS at seismic coefficient 0.21g corresponding to 6.5M earthquake = 0.99
- FOS at 33% saturation at the base of tension crack = 0.99.

The slopes are categorized as dry, semi saturated and saturated. The 33% saturation corresponds to semi-saturated conditions that may be assessed and not measured exactly unless samples at that time are taken and tested.

- Estimated volume to be moved = 4780400 m^3
- Rock block slide may totally block the river.

Table. 2: Field measurements and Evaluations of Discontinuity Parameters near Bridge

Joint Set No.	Strike	Dip	Spacing (Cm)	Persistence (m)	Aperture (mm)	Nature of infilling	Surface roughness	JRC	Schmidt Hardness	Length of Column above Joint Set (h)	JCS (MPa)	Normal Load KN*/m2	Ø Peak
Foliation	N70° W	73° NE	35	10	13	Un-filled	rough	8	17	5	20	125	42.6
Foliation	N72° W	76° NE	42	9	10	Un-filled	rough	4	16	4.5	18	112.5	33.8
J-1	N81° E	48° SE	80	2	9	Un-filled	rough	6	17	5	19	125	38
J-2	N78° E	40° SE	75	5	12	Un-filled	rough	5	16	4	18	100	36.3 9

Fig. 10: Plot between seismic coefficient and Factor of safety

Fig. 11: Slope stability analysis

Conclusions

Following conclusions have been drawn through field and laboratory studies;

1. the site is located in metasediments with patches and lenses of basic to ultramafic rocks. Slates, phyllites and schists are the dominant rocks which are moderately to highly foliated fractured and weathered.
2. Engineering character of rocks has been greatly affected by intense stresses due to presence of major structural features such as Main Karakorum thrust (MKT) and its off shoots. Local faults have also been developed showing minor displacements.
3. General trend of foliation in the area is north east with a number of joint sets oriented in different directions.
4. Intersection of foliation by two prominent joint sets besides random joints is responsible for rock fall and plan failures on all the three slopes of Hussainabad / Khizarabad site. However, small scale rotational movements of southern and western slopes are the result of highly fractured and weathered nature of rock on these spots.
5. Freezing of water in the fractures has significant role in the rock falls and plan failures and sometimes is a triggering factor.
6. The maximum block size generally is 1x1.5 m but larger block size (3x3m) is found on the slope little west of bridge on southern slope.
7. Occasional rock fall is common mode of slope movement but extensive rock fall may occur on earthquake vibrations, freezing of water in the crack and high recharge.
8. Tension cracks found on the upper slope are not persistent to the side slopes or the toe on both sides. They can generate large scale movement by their intersection with joint set J-1 dipping southward, provided shearing though intact parts between joints takes place. This phenomenon is likely to occur on earthquake of 6.5 magnitudes or 33% saturation.
9. In dry conditions, without seismic loading, slope is fairly stable with factor of safety of 1.34, however, saturation or strong motion can trigger the movement.
10. In case of large block slide, blockage of Hunza river near bridge site may cause damming.

Recommendations

1. In view of very large source area of rock fall, prevention of rock fall at the source seems to be financially impracticable. In the light of recent extensive rock falls and the maximum block size on source areas, range of influence is more or less same as the farthest houses already affected. The shelters or houses may be shifted towards river bank in the safe areas. The area between southern slope and the river should not be used for this purpose. The boundary of safe and unsafe area is marked on Fig. at the bottom
2. Gabian wall along the road passing through Hussainabad can protect the area on other side of the road from the influence of rock falls.
3. Similar gabian wall can protect the part of Khizarabad. The experience of previous extensive rock fall can be used for the location, height and strength of gabian structure.
4. Negative slope can be given to the area near the toe of the slope in order to bounce back the boulders instead of further rolling down the slope. The area under influence can only be used for cultivation. The naturally existing benches may be given negative slope in order to save the cast.
5. Monitoring of movement along the cracks should be initiated using simplest method. However more sophisticated techniques can also be used if possible such as; Extensometer, inclinometer, precision surveying and geo-space sensing etc. The simplest method of monitoring that can be adopted is the installation of deep monitoring pegs. Two numbers of pegs may be installed on stable mass and other two on moving mass. Straight and diagonal distance of the pegs should be weakly measured and recorded in order to identity any movements. The pegs should be imbedded about five feet in the firm ground at three distant locations.

6. Frequent rock falls and plane failures on southern slope particularly in Bridge area are very hazardous. Alternate bridge needs to be built upstream of Hussainabad in the safe area indicated on the map. Site selection should take into account the left abutment conditions and peak flood consideration.
7. The results of this study could be useful for a precise evaluation of possible landslides in other areas of Pakistan as well as in other parts of the world.

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References

- [1] Alexoudi M, et al.,. Landslide risk assessment and management of the Florina-Pisoderi-Kastoria roadline (Greece). *Journal of Environmental Protection and Ecology*, 2011; 12(1): 114-124.
- [2] Aleotti P. and R. Chowdhury. Landslide hazard assessment: summary review and new perspectives. *Bulletin of Engineering Geology and the environment*, 1999; 58(1): 21-44.
- [3] Nath SK. Seismic hazard mapping and microzonation in the Sikkim Himalaya through GIS integration of site effects and strong ground motion attributes. *Natural Hazards*, 2004; 31(2): 319-342.
- [4] Gupta R,B Joshi. Landslide hazard zoning using the GIS approach—a case study from the Ramganga catchment, Himalayas. *Engineering geology*, 1990;28(1-2). 119-131.
- [5] Owen L A, et al. Landslides triggered by the 8 October 2005 Kashmir earthquake. *Geomorphology*, 2008; 94(1-2): 1-9.
- [6] Dahal RK, S Hasegawa. Representative rainfall thresholds for landslides in the Nepal Himalaya. *Geomorphology*, 2008; 100(3-4): 429-443.
- [7] Akram MS, M. Zeeshan, A. Ali. Stability Analysis of Landslide near Dewal Village along Murree-Muzaffarabad Road, Pakistan. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, 2018; 91(6): 729-735.
- [8] Khan AN. Extent and evaluation of the adverse effects of landslides on housing in Murree, Pakistan. *Journal of Rural Development and Administration*, 1994;26(1): 199-140.
- [9] Khan A. Landslide hazard and policy response in Pakistan: a case study of Murree, Pakistan. *Sci Vis*, 2000; 6(1): 35-48.
- [10] Gabet EJ, et al. Rainfall thresholds for landsliding in the Himalayas of Nepal. *Geomorphology*, 2004; 63(3-4): 131-143.
- [11] Gattinoni P. Parametrical landslide modeling for the hydrogeological susceptibility assessment: from the Crati Valley to the Cavallerizzo landslide (Southern Italy). *Natural hazards*, 2009;50(1): 161-178.
- [12] Grøneng G., et al. Meteorological effects on seasonal displacements of the Åknes rockslide, western Norway. *Landslides*, 2011; 8(1): 1-15.
- [13] Kanungo D,et al. A fuzzy set based approach for integration of thematic maps for landslide susceptibility zonation. *Georisk*, 2009; 3(1): 30-43.
- [14] Lin, CW, et al. Impacts of the Chi-Chi earthquake on subsequent rainfall-induced landslides in central Taiwan. *Engineering Geology*, 2006; 86(2-3): 87-101.

- [15] Bhasin R, AM Kaynia. Static and dynamic simulation of a 700-m high rock slope in western Norway. *Engineering Geology*, 2004; 71(3-4): 213-226.
- [16] Ahmad M, M Ansari, and T Singh. Instability investigations of basaltic soil slopes along SH-72, Maharashtra, India. *Geomatics, Natural Hazards and Risk*, 2015; 6(2):115-130.
- [17] Kainthola, A., et al. Comparative Stability Analysis of Cut Slopes Using Different Numerical Approaches. *strain*, 2015;10: 5.
- [18] RK U, et al. Stability analysis of cut slopes using continuous slope mass rating and kinematic analysis in Rudraprayag district, Uttarakhand. *Geomaterials*, 2011;2011.
- [19] Sharma L, et al. Stability investigation of hill cut soil slopes along National highway 222 at Malshej Ghat, Maharashtra. *Journal of the Geological Society of India*, 2017; 89(2): 165-174.
- [20] Singh, P, et al. The stability of road cut cliff face along SH-121: a case study. *Natural hazards*, 2013; 68(2): 497-507.
- [21] Waseem M, et al. Slope Stability Analysis of the Qalandarabad Landslide. *Technical Journal*, 2021; 26(02): 1-17.
- [22] Kazmi AH, MQ Jan. *Geology and tectonics of Pakistan*. 1997;Graphic publishers.
- [23] Khan A, Atta-ur-Rahman (2006). Landslide hazards in the mountainous region of Pakistan.;*Pak J Geogr*. 16: 38-51.
- [24] Clerici A, et al. Landslide failure and runout susceptibility in the upper T. Ceno valley (Northern Apennines, Italy). *Natural hazards*, 2010; 52(1):1-29.
- [25] Msilimba G. The socioeconomic and environmental effects of the 2003 landslides in the Rumphu and Ntcheu Districts (Malawi). *Natural Hazards*, 2010;53(2):347-360.
- [26] Umrao RK, et al. Soil slope instability along a strategic road corridor in Meghalaya, north-eastern India. *Arabian Journal of Geosciences*, 2017;10(12):260.
- [27] Powell CM. A speculative tectonic history of Pakistan and surroundings. *Geodynamics of Pakistan*, 1979.
- [28] Ahmad M., et al. Assessment of reservoir temperatures of thermal springs of the northern areas of Pakistan by chemical and isotope geothermometry. *Geothermics*, 2002;31(5):613-631.
- [29] Khan AN. *Landslide Hazards and Policy-Response in Pakistan: A Case Study of Murree*. Commission on Science and Technology for Sustainable Development in the South, 1995;35.

